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BOKS MUSOBAQALARIDA HAKAMLARNING BAHOLANISHI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada boks sport turida xotin qizlarni hakamlikka tayyorlash qobiliyatini rivojlantirish masalasi muhokama qilinadi. Hozirgi kunda har qanday sport turida hakamlik muhim ahamiyatga ega hisoblanadi. Boks sport turidagi hakamlik faoliyatini yo'lga qo'yish texnik va taktik harakatlarini faollashtirish va yangi tizimni joriy qilish ko'zda tutilgan. Oldinga qo'yigan maqsad xotin qizlarning hakamlik darajasini oshirish va ularni boksdagi muvaffaqiyatlariga zamin yaratish.

Abstract. This article discusses the issue of developing the ability to prepare women for refereeing in boxing. Nowadays, refereeing is considered an important role in any sport. The establishment of refereeing activities in boxing is aimed at activating technical and tactical actions and introducing a new system. The goal is to increase the level of women's refereeing and create a basis for their success in boxing.

Kalit so'zlar: Boks musobaqalari, hakamlar, baholash kengashi, ringda harakatlanish, ringni kuzatish, referening majburiyatlari.

Ключевые слова: соревнования по боксу, судьи, оценочная комиссия, перемещение по рингу, наблюдение за рингом, обязанности рефери.

Keywords: Boxing competitions, judges, evaluation board, movement in the ring, ring observation, referee's duties.

Dolzarbliqi. Mamlakatimizda hozirgi kunda yoshlarning boksga bo'lgan ommaviy qiziqishini inobatga olib, iqtidorli sportchilarni aniqlash, yuqori malakali hakamlarni, tanlash va saralash tizimini yanada takomillashtirish, soha mutaxassislarini tayyorlash va ularning moddiy rag'batlantirilishini yaxshilash, shuningdek, o'zbek boksining dunyodagi yetakchiligini saqlab qolish va davom

ettirish maqsadida, boks infratuzilmasini yanada rivojlantirish hamda xalqaro talablarga moslashtirish, boks maktablarini, shu jumladan davlat-xususiy sheriklik shartlari asosida ko'paytirish, boks bo'yicha professional trenerlar va hakamlarni tayyorlash tizimini rivojlantirish, o'quv-uslubiy qo'llanmalar ishlab chiqish, ilmiy-metodologik bazani yanada kuchaytirish, ayollar boksini rivojlantirish yuzasidan uzoq yillarga mo'ljallangan istiqbolli rejalarni ishlab chiqish va amalga oshirish asosiy maqsadimiz hisoblanadi. O'zbekiston boks federatsiyasi boks maktablarida zamonaviy ilmiy yutuqlar va innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalangan holda yuqori malakali trener va hakamlar va boshqa mutaxassislarining kasbiy mahoratini doimiy oshirib borish maqsadida mahalliy va xorijiy mutaxassislar ishtirokida seminar, trening, master-klasslar, o'quv darslari tashkil etilishi juda katta ahamiyat kasb etadi. Dunyoda zamonaviy sport boks sportchining kuch chidamliligi asosiy vositalardan biridir. Yuqori sport natijalariga erishish uchun jismoniy fazilatlarni rivojlantirish muhim ahamiyatga ega, buning natijasida bokschilarda raqobatbardosh baxslarni o'tkazish faolligi orqali texnik harakatlarning muvaffaqiyati oshadi, bu zamonaviy sport kurashida muhim omil hisoblanadi. Ushbu masalani o'rganishda muhim mavzu bo'mish sport kurashchilarning jismoniy tayyorgarligini yaxshilashning samarali vositalari va usullarini izlashdir. Boks sport turi, ko'plab sport turlarida bo'lgani kabi, tana faoliyati darajasi va rejimini hisobga olgan holda etakchi jismoniy fazilatlar kuch chidamliligidir. [1]

Jahonda hakamlarni tayyorlashning juda ko'p miqdordagi elementlari qo'llaniladi va musobaqa jarayonida baholab boriladi. Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, bokschilarning ringdagi jang davomiyligi 3 daqiqa davom etadi. Musobaqalar dinamik ravishda, yuqori tezlikda, turli xil texnikalar bajariladi va ularni muvaffaqiyatli bajarish uchun yuqori darajadagi kuch rivojlanishi talab etiladi. Raqobatbardosh jangning yuqori sur'ati tufayli sportchilarga ajratilgan oz vaqt

davomida nafaqat jang olib borishini nazorat qilishlari, balki kuch chidamliligini namoyish etib, hujum va qarshi hujum harakatlarini faol ravishda amalga oshirishlari kerak. Boksning chidamliligi jang davomida yuqori tezlikda harakatlarni bajarish qobiliyati, shuningdek, musobaqa davomida bir nechta olishuvlarni faol o'tkazish qobiliyati sifatida qaraladi. Bokschilar baxs davomida har qanday vaqtda maksimal kuch sarflashlari kerak, ba'zan esa tezlikni va kuch ta'sirini oshirish kerak bo'lgan bir nechta janglarda ham. Shu bilan birga, sportchi umumiy va maxsus chidamlilik bilan birgalikda kuchga ega bo'lishi kerak. Shu munosabat bilan bokschilarning jismoniy fazilatlarini rivojlantirish vositalari va usullari jang san'atlaridagi harakatlarning tuzilishiga o'xshash bo'lishini talab etmoqda. [3]

Respublikamizda boks ommaviy sport turi sifatida nufuzli xalqaro musobaqalarda, jumladan, Olimpiya va Osiyo o'yinlari, Jahon va Osiyo chempionatlarida yurtimiz sharafini munosib himoya qilib kelishmoqda. «milliy terma jamoalarning o'quv-mashg'ulot, musobaqa va turnirlarga tayyorgarlik jarayoniga ilg'or innovatsion, ilmiy-metodik texnologiyalarni joriy etish hamda sportchilarni tibbiy va farmakologik ta'minlash, ularda sportchilarning ishtirokini davrida ilmiy jihatdan tahlil qilish bo'yicha mutaxassislar (trenerlar, shifokorlar, fiziologlar, diyetologlar, ilmiy tahlilchilar va boshqalar) guruhlarini tashkil etish;». Mamlakatimiz boks sport turida yuqori natijalarga erishishida, ularni ilmiy jihatdan ta'minlash ham muhim o'rin egallaydi va uni doimiy takomillashuvi talab qilinadi. Sportning har xil turlari, jumladan sport kurashi bo'yicha sport zahiralari va O'zbekistonning Milliy terma jamoalarini tayyorlashni ilmiy ta'minlashni takomillashtirishning asosiy vazifalaridan biri zamonaviy yuqori natijalar sport tizimida raqobatbardoshlikni oshirish hisoblanadi. Boks sport turi bo'yicha xalqaro darajadagi, Jahon va Osiyo musobaqalarida raqobatbardosh hakamlarni tayyorlash ko'p yillik tayyorgarlik jarayonini boshqarish samaradorligi bilan belgilanadi.

Yuqoridagilardan kelib chiqqan holda, boks sport turida hakamlikni rivojlantirish bo'yicha ilmiy izlanishlarni amalga oshirish soha olimlari va mutaxassislarining muhim vazifalaridan biri bo'lib qolmoqda. [2]

Bilamiz hozirgi kunda boks sport turiga juda katta e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Sababi butun jahon arenalarida bizning boks ixlosmandlari yuqori cho'qqilarni zabt etmoqda. Shu boisdan hakamlik faoliyatiga ham extiyoj katta. Hakamlik faoliyati 3-5 yillardan buyon xotin qizlar orasida ham keng talqin qilinmoqda. Boks federatsiyasi hakamlarni baholash, ularni bilim darajasiga yetkazish uchun ko'plab o'quv semenarlari va treninglarni tashkil qilishmoqda. O'zbekiston chempionatlariga yevropadan kelgan hakamlar orasida ham ayol hakamlarning borligi bizga katta mativatsiya va hakamlikka qiziqishning yuqori bo'lishini taminlamoqda. Boks federatsiyasi tomonidan tashkil qilinayotgan seminar va treninglarda kamida 20 ga yaqin xotin qizlar eshtirok etib bilim saviyaga ega bo'lishmoqda.

Tadqiqotning maqsadi Boks sport turida xotin qizlarni hakamlikka tayyorlash, ayol qizlarimizning sonini ko'paytirish, taklif va tavsiyalar ishlab chiqishdan iborat.

Tadqiqot vazifalari:

- hakamlarning baholanishini tahlil qilish;
- hakamlikka xos jismoniy sifatlarni rivojlantirish;

Hozirgi kunda boks federatsiyasi tomonidan tashkil qilib kelingan musobaqalarda va O'zbekiston chempionatlarida, O'zbekiston kuboklarida, Xalqaro turnirlarda ishtirok etib xalqaro toifadagi hakamlikni qo'lga kiritgan 2 yulduzli IBA ayol hakamlarimiz bor. Bu bizning katta yutug'imiz va

qizlarimizning hech kimdan kam emasligining isbotidir. Hozirgi kunda boks sport turidan hakamlar faoliyatini boshlagan yosh hakamlarimizni baholash uchun boks federatsiyasi tomonidan baholovchi hakamlar qo'yilgan. Ular biz kabi yosh ayol hakamlarimizni ilm saviyasini tushunmagan boks termenlarini va musobaqalardagi tartib qoidalarini o'rgatib borishadi. Ringda harakatlanayotgan referening majburiyatlari kabi xato kamchiliklar ustida ishlab kelinmoqda. Birinchi marta hakamlar faoliyatini boshlayotgan referega ringni his qilishi uchun his hayajonni yo'q qilish, ularni ringda harakatlanishi uchun harakat qoidalarini o'rgatish, ringning majburiyatlarini tushuntirish, ringdagi boks hakami bokschini sindirib qo'ymasligi va ularni sog'ligi uchun javobgar shaxs ekanini hamisha yodda tutishi zarur. Chunki ringda harakat qilayotgan jang referesi shu darajada bo'lishi kerakki har tomonlama his qilish yon atrofdagilar, ringdagi bokschilar, baholovchi hakamlar, supir vayzerlar xullas hammani ko'zi bilan ko'rishi va his qilib turishi zarur bo'ladi. Ringdagi ayrim xato va kamchiliklar boksining mehnatini va umidini kelajagini barbod qilib qo'yishi mumkin. Shu boisdan ringda harakatni amalga oshiradigan referelar ringda umuman xato qilishga haqli emas. Bu uchun refere yetarli bilim darajaga ega bo'lishi kerak bo'ladi. Bundan tashqari ringda harakatlanayotgan refere ringning majburiyatlariga bo'ysinishi zarur. Bu majburiyatlar chiroyli toza va ozoda kiyinish madaniyati, ayol hakamlarning soch turmaklari, muomila madaniyati, ovoz balandligi bokschilar ringda refere borligini his qilib turishi, to'g'ri jis harakatlarini ko'rsatish, kabilar kiradi. Jangni olib borayotgan jang referesini baholash ringda harakatni boshlagandan boshlanadi. Refere ringga kutarilishi bilan ringni kuzdan kechirishi, bokschilarni kiyinishi shlim, perchatka kabilarni to'g'ri ekanligiga ishonch hosil qilib, jang referesi bokschilarni ring markasiga chaqirib boks termenlarni tushuntiradi, keyin qo'lini ko'tarib super vayzerga tayyor ekanligini va sekundamenrda turgan texnik hodimga qarab vaqtni bosishini aytadi. Jang shu bilan birinchi raund bahslari boshlanadi. Jang mobaynida jangni to'g'ri tashkil qilish referening asosiy vazifasi hisoblanadi. Musobaqada har doimgidek O'zbekiston boks federatsiyasi va hakamlar hay'ati tomonidan baholash me'zonlari ishlab chiqilgan va har bir musobaqada xakamlarni muntazam ravishda baholab boriladi. Bu ham musobaqaning saviyali o'tishiga va pedagogik jihatdan yondashganda yetuk kadr bo'lishini ta'minlaydi. Xotin qizlar o'rtasida o'tkaziladigan musobaqalar har doim erkaklarga nisbatan ancha qiyinroq bo'ladi. Musobaqada ayol hakamlar ko'proq hissiyotlarga berilganliklari va ayollik qalbi bo'lgani uchun hamisha ko'rsatgich foizlari 30%-40% erkaklarga nisbatan past bo'ladi. Bu musobaqaga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. 60%-70% noto'g'ri harakatlarni keltirib chiqaradi. O'tkazilgan tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra ringda harakatlanayotgan ayol referelarning majburiyatlarini

takomillashtirish turli musobaqalarda xakamlarda kuzatiladigan xato kamchiliklarni izlab topish va ularni bartaraf qilish, xamda ular faoliyatini takomillashtirish uchun tavsiyalarni izlab topish va ularni amaliyotda qo'llash bizning tadqiqotimizning maqsadi hisoblanadi.

Amaliy tavsiyalar: O'zbekiston Boks Federatsiyasi qoshida ayollar uchun maxsus hakamlik tayyorlov kurslarini yo'lga qo'yish; Ayol qizlarni bo'sh vaqtlarini mazmunli o'tkazish; Har bir o'quv dasturiga psixologik tayyorlov bo'limini kiritish; Ayol hakamlar uchun mentorlik (tajribali hakamlar rahbarligida) tizimini joriy etish; Hakamlik faoliyatida gender tengligi siyosatini qo'llab-quvvatlash.

XULOSA

Boks sport turida asosan refere bo'lish uchun birinchi navbatda amaliy bilan birga nazariy bilimlar mavjud bo'lishi kerak. Ringda harakatlanayotgan refereni asosiy vazifasi bokschining sog'ligi va ringda janglarni xavf xatarlarsiz chiroyli qilib o'tkazishi hisoblanadi. Buning uchun juda ko'plab tajriba talab etiladi. Ringda harakatlanayotgan referi diqqatni jamlab ustoz hakamlar tomonidan o'tkazilgan semenarlarda o'qib bilim tajribasini oshirishi kerak. Shunday qilib, ishlab chiqilgan o'quv-metodik model xotin-qizlarning boksdagi hakamlik faoliyatini samarali yo'lga qo'yish, ularning kasbiy salohiyatini oshirish va sportda gender tenglikni ta'minlashda muhim omil bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati

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Section: History of Language and Turkic Language Studies

UNITS THAT HAVE BEEN SIMPLIFIED AS A RESULT OF THE HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE LANGUAGE

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Abstract

This article discusses, through examples, the phenomenon of simplification that occurs when the base of a word partially or completely loses its independent lexical meaning as a result of morphological changes in its structure. It also explains that during the historical development of the language, morphological processes such as the disappearance of morphemes within words, the weakening of relationships between them, and phonetic changes or reductions have taken place, as well as the emergence of resegmentation phenomena.

Keywords: dialectism, argotism, historical root, simplification, morpheme, resegmentation phenomenon, word structure, lexical unit, adjective-forming affix, phonetic change, morphemic structure, reflexive voice.

At present, it is known that the Uzbek literary language contains more than 80,000 lexical units in general usage, taking into account the words that have been fully assimilated from other languages into Uzbek. Naturally, although the majority of these words are recorded in the latest edition of *The Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language*, their frequency of use varies. Accordingly, in linguistics, all lexical units are divided into two layers based on their usage: those that are unrestricted in use and those that are restricted.

Words with restricted usage include technical terms, professional vocabulary, dialectisms, argotisms, and historical words. The words in common use in modern Uzbek can also be divided into those with a high frequency of usage and those with a low frequency. The independent words that we consider to have undergone simplification in the course of historical development for various reasons — that is, roots, historical roots, and simplified words — amount to more than two thousand.

For instance, words such as *salanglamoq*, *sallamno*, *savoq*, *soldov*, *sarbon*, *sarboz*, *sopqin*, *so'loq*, *ko'ksov*, *ipirisqi*, *ko'laga*, *ko'rmana*, *ko'va*, *jilvir*, *yor g'uchoq*, *yovg'on*, *vofurush*, *go'sxo'r*, *do'lta*, *olacha*, *bulduruq*, *bujg'un*, *chaksa*, *cho'liq*, *shotir*, *shumgiya*, *yukun*, *urpoq*, *uchuq*, *erish*, *tepchik*, *taqim*, *yamlamaq*, *qursoq*, *qo'nqaymoq*, *oqova*, *miyiq*, and *paqqos* differ significantly in their frequency of use from words such as *og'iz*, *ag'dar*, *pichoq*, *ulug'*, *unday*, *uydirma*, *uchqun*, *uzum*, *uyg'un*, *uyg'oq*, *ulg'aymoq*, *o'smir*, *yasha*, *bo'yoq*, *quvnoq*, *qattiq*, *yaxshi*, *yomon*, *o'yin*, *qorishma*, *qo'ltiq*, *tilak*, *tizgin*, *tomoq*, *chirkin*, *epchil*, *chalkash*, *uyushiq*, *chaqqon*, *belgi*, *achinmoq*, *issiq*, *sovuq*, *alanga*, and *aslida*. In other words, the former group of words is used much less frequently.

All of these units, in fact, have undergone simplification as a result of historical development, and each occupies a unique place within the lexical composition of the modern Uzbek literary language, with differing levels of usage. Therefore, simplification influences the degree of word usage and tends to remain in a relatively neutral state.

As a result of changes that occur in the morphological structure of a word, the root may partially or completely lose its independent lexical meaning and fall out of use, while the affix loses its affixal function. During the course of historical development, when the root that once served as the base for a derived word disappears from the lexical stock of the language, this too causes structural changes in the morphology of the word.

For example, the word *yuqori* (“high”) was historically composed of a root (*yuq*, *yoq* meaning “elevated” — *yoq yer* = “high place”) and a formative affix (*-ora*, *-aru* — an ancient Turkic case suffix denoting direction). However, in the modern literary Uzbek language, both the root and the affix have fallen out of usage, merging together to form a single simple root. Words such as *yaqin* (“near”), *bezgak* (“malaria”), and *yosti* (“pillow”) were also historically bimorphemic; their roots (*yaq* — *yaqdi*, *yaqinlashdi*; *bez* — *bezdi*, *titradi*) have lost their ability to function independently as meaningful lexical units in contemporary Uzbek. As a result, they have merged with their affixes to form simple words.

In modern Uzbek, the morphological changes occurring within words can be summarized as follows:

1. One type of morphological change involves the resegmentation of morphemes within a word. This phenomenon occurs when one or several sounds from within a morpheme separate and attach to another morpheme, thereby altering the internal structure and boundaries of the morphemes. In such cases,

while the word (or stem) retains its derivative nature, the internal morphemes become redivided or reanalyzed.

For instance, words like *supurindi* (“sweepings”), *chayindi* (“rinsings”), and *qirindi* (“shavings”) can be morphologically segmented as *supur-in-di*, *chayi-n-di*, and *qir-in-di* respectively, based on their meaningful components — consisting of a root morpheme, a derivational morpheme, and a form-building morpheme. Similarly, in verbs like *shodlandi* (“rejoiced”) and *otlandi* (“mounted”), the structure can historically be divided into four morphemes (*shod-la-n-di*, *ot-la-n-di*). Over time, the derivational suffix *-la* absorbed the reflexive affix *-n*, leading to a simplification of the structure to *shod-lan-di* and *ot-lan-di*.

In the words *kelgindi* (“newcomer”), *chiqindi* (“waste”), and *belanchak* (“cradle”), we observe similar processes — one morpheme has absorbed another, forming complex affixes such as *-indi* and *-lan*.

The process of morphemic resegmentation in language contributes to the emergence of new derivational affixes, which gradually become productive over time. In modern Uzbek, complex suffixes such as *-lash* (e.g., *gaplash* — “to converse,” *salomlash* — “to greet,” *faollash* — “to become active”), *-lashtirish* (e.g., *gazlashtirish* — “to gasify,” *avtomatlashtirish* — “to automate”), and *-chilik* (e.g., *dehqonchilik* — “farming,” *qo‘shnichilik* — “neighborliness”) emerged precisely through such resegmentation, where one affix has absorbed another.

In the examples above, the affixal part of the word is no longer divided into separate morphemes; rather, it is regarded as a single, unified morpheme.

2. The second type of change that occurs in the morphological structure of a word is the process by which a derived word becomes a root (simple) word. This morphological process takes place as follows:

When the lexical meaning expressed by the base of a derived word becomes blurred or completely lost, and the derived form itself falls out of use as a transparent derivative, it turns into a simple, indivisible word.

For example, the words *qizil* (“red”) and *yashil* (“green”) are, from a historical perspective, relative adjectives derived from verbs. Over the course of linguistic evolution, the verbal bases that originally carried independent lexical meanings lost this property, and together with the adjective-forming affixes, came to express a single adjectival concept. Thus, a previously bimorphemic derived word transformed into a monomorphemic root word.

Throughout the historical development of the language, morphological processes such as the disappearance of morphemes within a word, the weakening of relationships between morphemes, and phonetic changes or reductions within the word have occurred. As a result, these processes lead to changes in the word’s

morphological structure and cause compound or derived words to transform into root (simple) words — in other words, to undergo simplification.

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**ИНТЕРНЕТ ТАРМОҚЛАРИ ВОСИТАСИДА СОДИР ЭТИЛАДИГАН
ОММАВИЙ ТАРТИБСИЗЛИКЛАРНИНГ КРИМИНОЛОГИК
ЖИҲАТЛАРИ**

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**КРИМИНОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ МАССОВЫХ БЕСПОРЯДОК,
СОВЕРШАЕМЫХ ЧЕРЕЗ СЕТИ ИНТЕРНЕТА**

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**CRIMINOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF COMMITTED MASS MASS MASS
MISCLAIMS THROUGH THE INTERNET NETWORK**

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Мазкур мақолада интернет тармоқлари орқали содир этиладиган оммавий тартибсизликларнинг криминалогик жиҳатлари комплекс таҳлил қилинади. Хусусан, ахборот-коммуникация технологияларининг жадал ривожланиши шароитида ижтимоий тармоқлар, мессенжерлар ва бошқа онлайн платформалар орқали оммавий тартибсизликларни ташкил этиш, унга даъват қилиш ва мувофиқлаштиришнинг шакл ва усуллари ўрганилади. Мақолада бундай жиноятларнинг сабаб ва шарт-шароитлари, шахс омиллари, ижтимоий-психологик ва ахборот хавфсизлиги билан боғлиқ омиллар ёритилади. Шунингдек, интернет орқали содир этиладиган оммавий тартибсизликларнинг криминалогик профилактикаси, уларни олдини олишда давлат органлари ва фуқаролик жамияти институтларининг ўрни таҳлил қилинади. Тадқиқот натижасида миллий қонунчиликни такомиллаштириш ҳамда профилактик чора-тадбирларни кучайтириш бўйича илмий-амалий таклифлар илгари сурилади.

Калит сўзлар: интернет тармоқлари, оммавий тартибсизликлар, криминология, кибержиноятчилик, ижтимоий тармоқлар

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье проводится комплексный анализ криминологических аспектов массовых беспорядков, совершаемых через интернет-сети. В частности, изучаются формы и методы организации, подстрекательства и координации массовых беспорядков через социальные сети, мессенджеры и другие онлайн-платформы в условиях стремительного развития информационно-коммуникационных технологий. В статье освещаются причины и условия таких преступлений, личностные факторы, социально-психологические факторы и факторы, связанные с информационной безопасностью. Также будет проанализирована криминологическая профилактика массовых беспорядков, совершаемых через Интернет, роль государственных органов и институтов гражданского общества в их предотвращении. В результате исследования будут выдвинуты научно-практические предложения по совершенствованию национального законодательства и усилению профилактических мер.

Ключевые слова: интернет, массовые беспорядки, криминология, киберпреступность, социальные сети

ABSTRACT

This article comprehensively analyzes the criminological aspects of mass riots committed through internet networks. In particular, the forms and methods of organizing, inciting, and coordinating mass riots through social networks, messengers, and other online platforms in the context of rapidly developing information and communication technologies are being studied. The article covers the causes and conditions of such crimes, personal factors, socio-psychological factors, and factors related to information security. Also, the criminological prevention of mass riots committed through the Internet, the role of state bodies and civil society institutions in their prevention will be analyzed. As a result of the research, scientific and practical proposals will be put forward to improve national legislation and strengthen preventive measures.

Keywords: internet, mass riots, criminology, cybercrime, social networks

Ахборот-коммуникация технологияларининг жадал ривожланиши, айниқса интернет ва ижтимоий тармоқларнинг кенг оммалашуви жамият ҳаётининг барча соҳаларига чуқур таъсир кўрсатмоқда. Интернет нафақат ахборот алмашиш, мулоқот ва таълим воситаси, балки айрим ҳолларда жиноий фаолиятни ташкил этиш ва мувофиқлаштириш учун ҳам қўлланилаётган муҳим майдонга айланмоқда. Айниқса, интернет тармоқлари орқали оммавий тартибсизликларни келтириб чиқариш, унга даъват қилиш ёки бундай ҳаракатларни бошқариш замонавий жиноятчиликнинг хавфли кўринишларидан бири сифатида намоён бўлмоқда.

Оммавий тартибсизликлар кенг кўламли ҳодиса бўлиб, катта гуруҳлар томонидан амалга ошириладиган, аввало, жамоат хавфсизлиги асосларига таҳдид солувчи ва ҳокимият органлари, муассасалар ҳамда бошқа ташкилотлар фаолиятини беқарорлаштиришга, шунингдек, сезиларли ҳудудларда жамоат тартибини бузишга қодир бўлган турли хил ижтимоий хавфли хатти-ҳаракатлар мажмуини ўз ичига олади¹.

Ташқи томондан, оммавий тартибсизликлар ўз-ўзидан пайдо бўлаётганга ўхшайди, айниқса улар бир-бирига ҳеч қандай алоқаси йўқдек туюлган кўплаб кўринишларда намоён бўлади. Унда ҳеч ким бошқармайдиган хатти-ҳаракатлар (зўравонлик, қирғин, ўт қўйиш, мулкни йўқ қилиш, қурол-яроғ, портловчи қурилмалар, портловчи, захарловчи ва атрофдагилар учун хавфли бўлган бошқа моддаларни қўллаш, полиция ходимларига ёки ҳокимиятнинг бошқа вакилларига қуролли қаршилик кўрсатиш) акс этиши мумкин. Бироқ, Россия Федерацияда суд амалиёти ва жамоат тартибини сақлаш бўйича полиция бўлинмаларининг 115 нафар вакили билан ўтказилган сўров натижаларини ўрганиш бунинг аксини кўрсатмоқда. Сўровда қатнашган 97 нафар (84,34%) респондентнинг фикрича, аксарият ҳолларда оммавий тартибсизликлар олдиндан режалаштирилган, ташкил этилиш хусусиятга эга².

Оммавий тартибсизликлар одатда катта гуруҳдаги шахслар иштирокида жамоат тартиби ва хавфсизлигига қарши қаратилган зўравонлик, талон-тарож, ўт қўйиш, қонунга бўйсунмаслик каби ҳаракатлар билан

¹ Борисов С.В., Дмитренко П.А., Осипов В.А., Русскевич Е.А. Квалификация массовых беспорядков, хулиганства и преступлений экстремистской направленности: теория и практика: Учеб. пособие. М.: ИД «Юриспруденция», 2012.

² Кабанов Н.А. Массовые беспорядки, совершаемые с использованием информационно-коммуникационных технологий, как объект криминологического исследования // Юридические науки. 2019, №2. – С. 136-140.

ифодаланади. Анъанавий шаклларда бундай ҳаракатлар кўча, майдон ёки бошқа жамоат жойларида юзага келган бўлса, замонавий шароитда интернет ушбу жиноятларни тайёрлаш ва амалга оширишнинг асосий воситаларидан бирига айланмоқда.

Интернет орқали оммавий тартибсизликлар қуйидаги шаклларда намоён бўлиши мумкин:

- ижтимоий тармоқлар орқали оммавий тартибсизликларга даъват қилиш;
- ёлғон ёки таҳқирловчи ахборот тарқатиш орқали аҳоли орасида беқарорликни кучайтириш;
- мессенжерлар орқали гуруҳли ҳаракатларни мувофиқлаштириш;
- видео, аудио ва визуал контент орқали зўравонликка ундаш.

Ижтимоий хавфлиликнинг юқори даражаси ва оммавий тартибсизликларнинг кўлами уларга қарши курашишнинг самарали чораларини, биринчи навбатда, юқорида таъкидланган ушбу жиноятларнинг очик ёки яширин уюшган хусусиятини ҳисобга олган ҳолда олдини олувчи, профилактик хусусиятга эга бўлган, шу жумладан ахборот жамияти даврининг атрибути бўлган ахборот-коммуникация технологияларидан фойдаланишга асосланган чораларни ишлаб чиқиш ва доимий такомиллаштириш заруратини келтириб чиқаради³.

Ахборот-коммуникация технологияларидан жинойий мақсадларда фойдаланишдан келиб чиқадиган таҳдидлар тўғрисида кўплаб ҳужжатларда қайд этилади, жумладан, бундай технологиялар оммавий тартибсизликларга тайёргарлик кўришда, уларнинг иштирокчиларини ўқитишда, оммавий тартибсизликларни ташкил этишда, уларга даъват қилишда ва уларни бошқаришда қўлланилиши мумкинлигини ҳисобга олиш зарур. Шу билан бирга, Интернет тармоғи ва бошқа ахборот-коммуникация технологияларидан фойдаланган ҳолда содир этиладиган оммавий тартибсизликларнинг криминологик ва жиноят-ҳуқуқий хусусиятларини аниқлаш ва очиб бериш илмий ва амалий қизиқиш уйғотади.

Вақт ўтиши билан оммавий тартибсизликлар иштирокчиларининг ўзаро ҳамкорлиги, уларнинг сафига янги аъзоларни жалб этиш, режалаштирилаётган тажовузлар жойлари ва объектлари ҳақида маълумотларни излаш ва тўплаш, экстремистик мазмундаги матнли, график, аудиовизуал материалларни тайёрлаш ва тарқатиш учун ахборот-

³ *Иванцов С.В.* Средства массового информационного ресурса и противодействие преступности: Сб. мат. V Междунар. науч.-практ. конф. «Современные проблемы уголовной политики» / Под ред. А.Н. Ильяшенко. Краснодар, 2014.

коммуникация технологияларининг кенг имкониятларидан фаол фойдаланишнинг барқарор тенденцияси кузатилмоқда.

Ахборот-коммуникация технологияларидан фойдаланиш туфайли тайёргарлик ва ташкилий ҳаракатлар оммавий тартибсизликлар жойидан исталган масофада амалга оширилиши мумкин, бошқа давлатлар худудидан жиноий фаолиятни бошқаришни истисно қилмаган ҳолда, асосан яширин хусусиятга эга бўлади ва кўпинча тартибсизликлар тугаганидан кейингина аниқланади. Бу ҳолат бундай жиноятларнинг олдини олишни сезиларли даражада мураккаблаштиради; уларни содир этиш сабаблари ва шарт-шароитларининг ўзига хос хусусиятларини, шунингдек оммавий тартибсизликлар доирасида жиноий жазоланадиган қилмишларни тайёрлаётган ва содир этаётган субъектларнинг шахсини ҳисобга олган ҳолда, ахборот-коммуникация технологияларидан фойдаланган ҳолда такомиллаштириш зарурлигини тақозо этади.

Оммавий тартибсизликларнинг олдини олиш бўйича мавжуд ҳуқуқий, ташкилий ва махсус криминологик чора-тадбирларни ишлаб чиқишни айбдор шахслар томонидан тегишли жиноятларни тайёрлаш ва бевосита амалга оширишнинг янги усулларидан фойдаланиш шароитида уларнинг самарадорлигини илмий тадқиқ этиш асосида амалга ошириш зарур.

Ўзбекистон Республикаси Жиноят кодекси 244-моддасида оммавий тартибсизларга доир махсус қоидалар кўрсатилган бўлиб, унга кўра, оммавий тартибсизликларга ва фуқароларга нисбатан зўравонлик қилишга омма олдида даъват қилиш, шахсининг оммавий тартибсизликлар содир этиш мақсадида ўқувдан ўтиши, шу жумладан оммавий тартибсизликларни содир этиш билимини, амалий маҳоратини ва кўникмаларини эгаллаши, ўқув чоғида қурол-яроғ, портлатиш қурилмалари, портловчи, заҳарловчи, атрофдагилар учун хавф туғдирадиган бошқа моддалар ва буюмлар билан муомала қилиш усулларини ўрганиши, қурол ёки қурол сифатида фойдаланиладиган бошқа нарсаларни ишлатиб ёхуд ишлатиш билан кўрқитиб шахсга нисбатан зўрлик ишлатиш, қирғин солиш, ўт қўйиш, мулкка шикаст етказиш ёки уни нобуд қилиш, ҳокимият вакилига қаршилик кўрсатиш орқали содир этилган оммавий тартибсизликларни ташкил қилиш ёхуд ушбу фаолиятни молиялаштириш, худди шунингдек оммавий тартибсизликларда фаол қатнашиш учун жиноий жавобгарлик белгиланган⁴.

Оммавий тартибсизликлар билан боғлиқ Россия Федерацияси Жиноят кодексининг 212-моддасига кетма-кет ўзгартиришлар киритилди. Хусусан,

⁴ Ўзбекистон Республикасининг Жиноят кодекси. <https://www.lex.uz/acts/111453>

2013, 2014 ва 2016 йилларда киритилган “Оммавий тартибсизликлар”, шу жумладан оммавий тартибсизликларни ташкил этишга ундаш, ёллаш ва бошқача тарзда жалб қилиш, шунингдек бундай тартибсизликларни кейинчалик ташкил этиш ёки уларда бошқача тарзда иштирок этиш учун ўқитиш учун жавобгарлик тўғрисидаги қоидалар киритилган. Ушбу норма терроризм ва экстремизмга қарши кураш чораларини кучайтириш билан узвий боғлиқ ҳолда янгиланган бўлса-да, у Жиноят кодексининг террористик ва экстремистик фаолиятни амалга оширишга оммавий даъватлар учун жавобгарлик тўғрисидаги махсус моддалардан фарқли ўлароқ, ахборот-телекоммуникация тармоқларидан фойдаланган ҳолда содир этилган ҳаракатларнинг, шу жумладан оммавий тартибсизликларга даъватларнинг юқори ижтимоий хавфини ҳисобга олган ҳолда жиноий жавобгарликни табақалаштиришни назарда тутмайди.

Бир қатор олимларнинг фикрича, кўрсатилган нормаларда террористик ёки экстремистик фаолиятга оммавий даъватлар учун жавобгарликни белгилаш терроризмни, шу жумладан ҳудудий яхлитликни бузадиган хатти-ҳаракатларга қарши курашиш, шунингдек, ахборот-телекоммуникация тармоқларидан фойдаланган ҳолда бундай хатти-ҳаракатларни содир этиш кўринишидаги терроризмни шахсий оқлаш ва тарғиб қилиш, катта гуруҳларни жамоат хавфсизлигини, конституциявий тузум асосларини ва давлатимиз хавфсизлигини жиддий бузишга қодир бўлган ижтимоий хавфли хатти-ҳаракатларга ундовчи тегишли тажовузларнинг юқори ижтимоий хавфи туфайли ўзини оқлаган қонуний чора бўлди.

Ҳозирги вақтда бундай қилмишларни амалга оширишнинг мураккаб механизмини, шу жумладан нафақат жиноий режаларни амалга ошириш режалаштирилаётган давлат ҳудудида, балки бошқа мамлакатларда ҳам амалга оширилаётган оммавий тартибсизликлар ташкилотчилари ва иштирокчиларини ўқитиш ва бошқа тайёргарликни ўз ичига олган узоқ муддатли босқичма-босқич тайёргарлик фаолиятини ҳисобга олиш лозим⁵. Бу дастлаб ижтимоий тармоқларда, турли сайтларда ва Интернет тармоғининг бошқа ресурсларида ўз аксини топмоқда.

Оммавий тартибсизликларнинг олдини олиш бўйича мавжуд ташкилий ва махсус криминологик чора-тадбирлар асосан турли спорт, маданий ва бошқа оммавий тадбирлар ҳамда оммавий акциялар ўтказиш жараёнида, шунингдек озодликдан маҳрум қилиш жазосини ижро этувчи муассасалар

⁵ Горемычкин И.Е. Соотношение уголовно-правовых норм о групповых преступлениях Общей и Особенной частей УК РФ (на примере статьи о массовых беспорядках) // Российский следователь. 2017. № 13. С. 23–26.

шароитида бундай тартибсизликларнинг олдини олиш ва уларга чек қўйишга қаратилган бўлиб, уларни тайёрлаш имкониятлари ва хусусиятларини ҳисобга олмайди. Кишилар тўпланадиган бундай жойлардан ва (ёки) кўрсатилган тадбирлар вақтидан ташқарида ахборот-коммуникация технологияларидан фойдаланган ҳолда тартибсизликларни бевосита амалга ошириш мумкин.

Ахборот-коммуникация технологияларидан фойдаланиш ҳозирги вақтда ижтимоий хавфлилик даражасини оширувчи турли йўналишдаги жиноятларни тайёрлаш ва бевосита содир этишнинг типик усули сифатида аҳамият касб этмоқда, айниқса ижтимоий тармоқларда одамларнинг катта гуруҳларига уларни у ёки бу ноқонуний фаолиятга ундаш мақсадида таъсир ўтказишда, шу жумладан оммавий тартибсизликларни ташкил этиш ва уларда иштирок этишда қуролга айланмоқда⁶.

Ахборот-коммуникация технологиялари оммавий тартибсизликларнинг бўлажак иштирокчиларини тайёрлаш ва ўқитиш, уларнинг сафларини янги аъзолар билан тўлдириш, улар ўртасида ўзаро ҳамкорликни йўлга қўйиш ва қўллаб-қувватлаш, нафрат ва адоват уйғотиш, шунингдек, зўравонлик ва бошқа оммавий тус олиши мумкин бўлган ижтимоий хавфли хатти-ҳаракатларга ундовчи бошқа паст ниятларни қўзғатиш учун фаол қўлланилмоқда.

Интернет воситасида содир этиладиган оммавий тартибсизликлар бир қатор криминологик хусусиятларга эга. Биринчидан, ушбу жиноятлар юқори даражада латент ҳисобланади. Чунки жиноятга даъват ёки тайёргарлик жараёнлари виртуал муҳитда, яширин гуруҳлар ёки ёпиқ каналлар орқали амалга оширилади.

Иккинчидан, бундай жиноятлар тезкорлик ва кенг қамровлилик билан ажралиб туради. Интернет орқали тарқатилган ахборот қисқа вақт ичида минглаб, ҳатто миллионлаб фойдаланувчиларга етиб бориши мумкин, бу эса оммавий тартибсизликларнинг кескин ва назоратдан чиқиб кетишига олиб келади.

Учинчидан, интернетдаги анонимлик жиноят содир этувчиларнинг шахсини аниқлашни қийинлаштиради ва жавобгарлик ҳиссини сусайтиради. Бу эса жинойий хулқ-атворга мойилликни оширади.

Келтирилган ҳолатлар оммавий тартибсизликлар учун жавобгарлик тўғрисидаги қонунчиликни ва уни қўллаш амалиётини такомиллаштириш

⁶ Суходолов А.П., Иванцов С.В., Борисов С.В., Спасенников Б.А. Актуальные проблемы предупреждения преступлений в сфере экономики, совершаемых с использованием информационно-телекоммуникационных сетей // Всероссийский криминологический журнал. 2017. Т. 11. № 1. С. 13–21.

бўйича илмий асосланган тавсиялар ва таклифлар мажмуасини шакллантириш зарурлигини тасдиқлайди, бунда бундай тартибсизликларнинг олдини олиш устувор йўналиш бўлиши керак, уларни тайёрлаш, ташкил этиш ва бевосита амалга оширишда ахборот-коммуникация технологияларидан фойдаланилади. Хулоса қилиб айтганда, интернет тармоқлари воситасида содир этиладиган оммавий тартибсизликлар замонавий жинойтчиликнинг мураккаб ва кўп қиррали кўриниши бўлиб, уларни фақат жиноий-хукукий чоралар билан эмас, балки кенг камровли криминологик профилактика орқали бартараф этиш мумкин. Ушбу соҳадаги илмий таҳлиллар ва амалий чора-тадбирлар жамият барқарорлиги ва хавфсизлигини таъминлашда муҳим аҳамият касб этади.

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PROCEDURAL FEATURES OF ISSUING A REASONED OPINION OF THE TAX AUTHORITY AND ITS LEGAL CONSEQUENCES IN TAX MONITORING

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ANNOTATION

This article analyzes the procedural framework governing the issuance of a reasoned opinion by the tax authority within the regime of tax monitoring in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The study elucidates the legal nature of the reasoned opinion as a quasi-administrative act that formalizes the official interpretation of tax legislation in relation to specific taxpayer transactions or obligations. Particular attention is paid to procedural guarantees ensuring transparency, legality, and protection of taxpayer rights during the preparation and issuance of such opinions, including deadlines, documentation requirements, and mechanisms of interaction between the taxpayer and the tax authority. The article further examines the legal consequences arising from the issuance of a reasoned opinion, including its binding or advisory character, the extent of reliance protection granted to the taxpayer, and its role in preventing tax disputes and administrative sanctions. By comparing the regime of reasoned opinions within tax monitoring with traditional forms of tax control, the research identifies their preventive and compliance-oriented function, contributing to enhanced legal certainty and cooperative tax administration. The findings emphasize the importance of clear procedural regulation to ensure predictability, fairness, and balance of interests between the fiscal authorities and taxpayers.

Key words: tax monitoring; reasoned opinion; tax authority; administrative procedure; tax control; legal consequences; taxpayer rights; procedural guarantees; compliance; legal certainty; preventive tax administration.

Tax monitoring occupies a special place in the system of tax control forms established by Article 136 of the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which provides for two main forms: tax audits and tax monitoring. This classification

reflects a modern approach to differentiating tax administration methods based on the nature of interaction between tax authorities and taxpayers. Unlike tax audits, which are unilateral and rely on the tax authority's authority, tax monitoring is characterized by bilateral cooperation and partnership-based interaction between the parties. The systemic place of tax monitoring is determined by its functional purpose as an alternative form of tax control, designed for large taxpayers with a high level of tax culture and a commitment to information transparency. In international tax administration practice, such forms of control are often referred to as "cooperative" or "joint" programs, emphasizing their difference from traditional coercive methods [1]. The place of tax monitoring in the tax control system can be characterized as the "highest form" of tax administration, assuming the most trusting relationship between the taxpayer and the tax authority.

The legal framework for tax monitoring in the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan is structured as a comprehensive legal institution, consisting of seven articles (169-175), which regulate all the main aspects of this form of tax control. The structural and logical structure of the legal regulation reflects the sequence of implementation of tax monitoring procedures: from general provisions and conditions of participation to specific dispute resolution procedures. Article 169 of the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan establishes the conceptual foundations of the institution, defining the subject, principles, and timeframe of tax monitoring. Article 170 of the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan regulates information exchange as the central element of the legal mechanism of tax monitoring. Article 171 of the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan details the decision-making procedure for conducting tax monitoring, including document requirements and grounds for refusal. Article 172 of the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides the grounds and procedure for early termination of tax monitoring. Articles 173-175 of the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan regulate procedural aspects of monitoring, including the procedure for drafting a reasoned

opinion and the mutual agreement procedure. This system of norms creates a comprehensive legal basis for the functioning of the institution of tax monitoring, but contains certain gaps and requires further development.

Legal regulation of tax monitoring in the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan is characterized by a combination of substantive and procedural rules, creating a holistic system of legal influence on tax monitoring relationships. Substantive rules define the rights and obligations of tax monitoring participants, establish criteria and conditions for participation, and regulate the legal consequences of various actions and decisions. Procedural rules detail the procedure for implementing substantive rights and obligations, establishing timeframes, document formats, and the sequence of procedural actions. A distinctive feature of legal regulation is the significant role of secondary rulemaking: the State Tax Committee is authorized to approve the application form for tax monitoring, the form and requirements for information exchange regulations, and the Cabinet of Ministers is authorized to approve the form and requirements for drafting a reasoned opinion. This model of legal regulation ensures the necessary flexibility in detailing procedures while maintaining the stability of the basic principles and approaches.

Tax monitoring and tax audits share a common legal goal: ensure taxpayers' compliance with tax legislation and the completeness of tax revenues to the state budget system. According to Article 135 of the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, tax control is the activity of authorized bodies to monitor compliance with tax legislation by taxpayers and tax agents, which applies equally to both tax monitoring and tax audits. Both institutions are based on a single legal foundation of tax legislation and are implemented within the scope of the tax authorities' powers established by the Tax Code. The subject of the control is also common: the accuracy of calculation, completeness, and timely payment of taxes and fees, compliance with tax accounting procedures, and filing of tax reports. International

practice shows that various forms of tax control, despite procedural differences, share a common focus on ensuring tax compliance and minimizing tax risks [2].

The traditional ex post tax control model is a system of measures implemented by tax authorities after the taxpayer has completed business transactions and submitted tax reports. These measures are aimed at identifying instances of incorrect calculation, incomplete or late payment of taxes, followed by the application of enforcement measures in the form of additional tax assessments, collection of penalties, and prosecution. The essential characteristics of this model are: retrospectiveness – control is carried out in relation to already completed transactions and expired tax periods; discreteness – control is carried out periodically in the form of individual control measures (office and on-site audits), rather than continuously; repressiveness – the focus is on identifying violations and applying sanctions, rather than on their prevention; confrontational nature – the tax authority and the taxpayer are in opposing positions, where the former seeks to identify violations and maximize additional assessments, and the latter – to minimize claims and avoid liability [3].

The ex ante preventive tax control model represents a fundamentally different approach based on continuous or preliminary information interaction between the tax authority and the taxpayer, aimed at identifying and resolving tax uncertainties before a formal violation or dispute arises. The key institutions of this model are: tax monitoring, which implies the tax authority's continuous access to the taxpayer's accounting information in real time; reasoned opinions and preliminary tax clarifications, which allow the taxpayer to obtain the tax authority's official position on contentious issues before a transaction or before the tax payment deadline; advance pricing agreements - preliminary agreements on transfer pricing; cooperative compliance programs based on voluntary disclosure of information in exchange for legal certainty and a reduced audit burden [4].

For taxpayers, the key advantage of the preventive model is ensuring legal certainty and predictability of tax liabilities. Under traditional ex post audits, taxpayers make decisions regarding the accounting and taxation of transactions amid uncertainty about how the tax authority will evaluate these decisions during a future audit, which may occur several years from now. The complexity and ambiguity of tax legislation, the multiple possible interpretations of individual provisions, and the variability of enforcement practices create significant risks that the taxpayer's position, which they considered reasonable at the time of the transaction, will be deemed incorrect by the tax authority during the audit. The preventive model radically reduces this uncertainty: through the institutions of reasoned opinion, preliminary tax clarification, and the approval of accounting policies, the taxpayer receives the official position of the tax authority before the transaction or before the tax payment deadline [5].

The study demonstrates that the preventive model of ex ante tax control represents a qualitatively new stage in the evolution of tax administration, meeting the challenges of the modern economy and reflecting the global trend of shifting from a repressive to a partner-based paradigm of government-business interaction. The conceptual difference between traditional ex post control and preventive ex ante control lies not simply in the change in the time frame of control, but in a fundamental transformation in the philosophy of tax administration: from the presumption of bad faith and a focus on identifying violations to the presumption of good faith and a focus on preventing violations through informational interaction and consultation.

Legal aspects of modern tax administration are characterized by the increasing role of administrative interpretation and consultative mechanisms. International practice demonstrates the growing importance of administrative acts, which provide legal certainty for taxpayers through the official clarification of tax authorities' positions on contentious issues. The evolution of administrative law in

the field of taxation demonstrates a trend toward the creation of hybrid legal instruments combining elements of consultation and control. Procedural aspects of tax control have significantly developed in the context of alternative dispute resolution and the introduction of mediation mechanisms. Research demonstrates the high effectiveness of out-of-court tax dispute resolution procedures, which reduce administrative costs and improve the quality of law enforcement. Particular attention is paid to the study of mutual agreement procedures as a tool for ensuring the fairness of the administrative process [6].

Despite significant research in the field of cooperative tax administration, the specific aspects of the tax authority's reasoned opinion as a legal instrument remain understudied. Existing studies primarily focus on the general principles of cooperative compliance, without paying due attention to a detailed analysis of the legal nature and procedural features of specific interaction mechanisms between tax authorities and taxpayers. This circumstance determines the relevance of a comprehensive study of the institution of the tax authority's reasoned opinion in the context of tax monitoring. The purpose of this study is to identify the legal nature of the tax authority's reasoned opinion in tax monitoring, characterize its procedural form, and determine the legal consequences of its application in the tax administration system of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The legal consequences of a reasoned opinion are characterized by conditional binding force and graduated legal force depending on the taxpayer's actions. If the taxpayer consents, the opinion becomes a binding administrative act, requiring changes to accounting and reporting. The implementation mechanism, through "taking into account the tax authority's position in accounting and tax reporting", creates broad scope for interpretation, which can lead to legal uncertainty. If the taxpayer disagrees, a mutual agreement procedure is activated, which is an administrative quasi-judicial proceeding involving a higher tax authority. This procedure reflects the principles of administrative fairness and

provides additional guarantees for the protection of taxpayer rights. Failure to comply with the agreed reasoned opinion creates legal grounds for the application of coercive measures, transforming the advisory instrument into a basis for administrative liability.

The procedural architecture of the motivated opinion system demonstrates an attempt to integrate elements of adversarial proceedings into the administrative and control activities of tax authorities. The ability to initiate a reasoned opinion by both the tax authority and the taxpayer creates a two-way communication model characteristic of modern tax administration concepts.

The impact of the motivated opinion mechanism on taxpayer behavior requires empirical study using behavioral economics methods. Theoretically, providing taxpayers with the opportunity to obtain the official position of the tax authority before the end of the tax period should reduce uncertainty and encourage voluntary compliance with tax laws. However, psychological factors, such as perceived procedural fairness and trust in tax authorities, can significantly influence taxpayers' willingness to participate in this mechanism. The potential "signaling" effect of obtaining a motivated opinion can both enhance tax compliance by demonstrating the tax authorities' attention to taxpayer activity and create negative incentives due to the perception of the procedure as an additional administrative burden.

The institutional aspects of the reasoned opinion process highlight the need to develop specialized competencies within tax authorities and modify their organizational structure. High-quality preparation of reasoned opinions requires tax officials to have in-depth knowledge not only of tax law but also of the specifics of doing business in various sectors of the economy. Ensuring uniformity in approaches to preparing reasoned opinions requires the development of internal standards and methodological materials, as well as the creation of a system for professional training and professional development for employees. The mutual

agreement procedure requires that employees of higher-level tax authorities possess mediation and alternative dispute resolution skills, which may require additional training. Organizational changes should also ensure the independence of officials conducting mutual agreement procedures from the employees who prepared the original reasoned opinions.

The prospects for the development of the motivated opinion system are linked to its potential integration into a broader digital tax administration system and the use of artificial intelligence technologies for tax risk analysis. Automating the process of identifying potential violations and generating preliminary motivated opinions can improve the efficiency of tax monitoring and ensure more uniform application of tax legislation. However, the implementation of such technologies requires careful development of decision-making algorithms and the provision of human oversight for automated processes. Developing international cooperation in tax administration can facilitate the exchange of best practices in the application of motivated opinions and the harmonization of approaches to cooperative compliance.

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Multispiral Computed Tomography Comparative Analysis and Justification of Chronic Lung Disease Complications in Patients with Covid-19 Pneumonia

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Due to the high mortality from COVID-19 pneumonia, adequate and timely diagnosis comes to the fore. At the same time, radiation research methods play a huge role in identifying signs of inflammatory changes in the lungs, determining the volume of lung damage, monitoring treatment and predicting the course of the disease. The most informative method of detecting changes in the lungs associated with COVID-19 is rightfully computed tomography of the thoracic cavity, which allows identifying typical manifestations of viral lung lesions [1,7]. However, in some cases, CT is problematic, especially in patients in the intensive care unit. In addition, due to the high radiation load, the question arises of limiting the use of this method in the framework of frequent control studies.

The purpose of the investigation. In order to reduce radiation exposure and obtain additional diagnostic information, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) was used in a number of patients [8].

Radiography is significantly inferior in the sensitivity of computed tomography, it allows us to confidently detect only severe forms of pneumonia [6]. Most of the available studies indicate that traditional lung radiography has low sensitivity at an early stage. Ultrasound examination (ultrasound) of the lungs is considered as an alternative to X-ray studies [2]. Important advantages of ultrasound compared to radiography are: zero radiation load, assessment of infiltration in Live mode, the ability to monitor the dynamics of pneumonia. [3]. Demonstrating high sensitivity in the diagnosis of pneumonia, ultrasound at the same time has its limitations — sensitivity parameters are significantly reduced with a small lesion of lung tissue, localization of pneumonia in areas difficult to reach for the ultrasound wave [3, 5]. In this regard, ultrasound in the diagnosis of coronavirus pneumonia requires a more detailed study.

Materials and methods

The clinical and radiation data of 27 patients (15 women and 12 men) who underwent COVID-19 and were observed in medical and preventive institutions of the city of Karaganda, Temirtau from August 2020 to December 2021 were analyzed. The average age of patients was 37.2 ± 15.7 years. All patients underwent high-resolution computed tomography (HRCT), which was performed with a thin slice of 1-2 mm at the inhalation delay in the pulmonary and mediastinal modes with a scanning area from the tops of the lungs to the sinuses, in the native mode on devices with 128 slices. Scanning was carried out on a GE Optima CT 660 computed tomograph

The consequence of the high density of recording for CT studies, as well as the temporary technical malfunction of CT machines caused by the increased round-the-clock load on X-ray tubes, was the inability to perform CT in some patients. It is in such a situation of lack of opportunities that magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) has become an alternative method of diagnosing pulmonary changes.

MRI examination of the chest organs was carried out in 9 patients on Toshiba Titan Vantage 1.5 T MRI scanners (Canon Medical), in T1-, T2-weighted modes (T1VI, T2VI), STIR-modes, in axial and frontal planes, with breath retention.

Radiography was performed in straight posterior and lateral projections, when the patient's condition allowed him to be in a vertical position, whereas in a straight anterior projection — with the patient's horizontal position. During X-ray examination, pneumonia was confirmed or excluded, the extent of darkening was estimated depending on the localization by segments, the presence of complications in the form of destructive processes, pleural effusion.

Ultrasound examination of the lungs was performed on a Toshiba AplioMX ultrasound machine using a 5 MHz convexic sensor.

Ultrasound assessed the localization of the process, the length of the infiltration site, as well as the number of B-lines and "air bronchograms" per unit area.

Radiation diagnostic methods were used strictly according to the indications and prescription of the attending physician, and patients or their legal representatives signed an informed consent to conduct the study. Results and discussion. Computed tomography.

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Lingvistika ekspertizasi va uning tarkibiy qismlari

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Turli ko'rinishdagi matnlarni ekspertiza qilish jarayoni o'zigaxos bosqichlarni qamrab olib, bu jarayon lingvistik tahlildan tamoman farq qiladi. Mavjud nazariy bilimlar amaliyotga tatbiq etilib, ekspert tomonidan umumlashmalar hosil qilinadi. Har qanday matn ham lingvistik ekspertiza o'tkazish ob'ekti bo'la olmaydi. Konfliktli og'zaki va yozma matnlar lingvistik ekspertiza o'tkazish uchun asos vazifasini bajara oladi. Og'zaki ko'rinishdagi matnlartelefonyozishmalari, audio va video xabarlar, favqulodda qo'ng'iroqlar turli irqiy kamsitish, haqorat, obro'sizlantirish, tashviqotlarga qaratilgan ommaviy murojaatnomalar bo'lishi mumkin. Yozma matnlar ko'lami esa biroz kengroq. Xususan, konfliktli yozmamatnlarning lingvistik ekspertizasini quyidagi turlarga ajratish mumkin:

- Turli shaxsiy yozishmalar;
- Anonim xatlar;
- Gazeta materiallari;
- Internet saytlarida e'lon qilingan xabarlar;
- E-mail pochталari orqali yuborilgan xatlar;

Qo'lyozma matnlar lingvistik ekspertizasida muallifning psixologik holati, yoshi, kasb turi kabi turli ma'lumotlarni aniqlash imkoniyati birmuncha yuqori. Qo'lyozma matnlar kriminilaistik tadqiqotida yozma nutqning umumiy va xususiy alomatlari ajralib turadi. Umumiy alomatlar nutq muallifining leksik, grammatik, stilistik imkoniyatlarini aniqlash va baholash imkoniyatini yuzaga keltiradi. Xususiy alomatlardanoadabiy unsurlar, ortiqcha so'zlar, iboralarni noto'g'ri ishlatish, so'zlar takrori, leksik so'z boyligi yetishmasligi kabi elemntlar uchraydi. Bu esa ekspertga muallif haqida umumiy jihatlarni ochishga yordam beradi. Asosiy qism. Lingvistik ekspertizani tarkibiy qismlarga ajratishda mutaxassislar tomonida turlicha yondashuvlar mavjud. Ushbu soha yigirmanchi asrning so'nggi o'nyilliklarida rivojlangan; Grachev M. Atalqinida esa lingvistik ekspertiza alohida

turga ajratilgan har xil turdagi tadqiqot materiallari, moddalar, mahsulotlar, shuningdek materialshunoslik deb bilan ish ko'radigan yuridik sohaning tarmoqlaridan biri. Biroq, yana bir nuqtai nazar -E. I. Galyashina va E. R. Rossinskayaning so'zlariga ko'ra, lingvistik ekspertiza -bu nutq tekshiruvlarisinfiga kiruvchiga ekspertizaning alohida turi. Germaniyalik olim Jurgen Handkie fukrlariga ko'ra, lingvistik ekspertizada ikkimuhim omil mavjud:

- Ovozli xabarlar identifikatsiyasi;
- Yuridik matnlar identifikatsiyasi;

Birinchi turda olim ovozning fonetik xususiyatlari, ovoz tempi va uzunligi kabilarga e'tibor qaratish lozimligiga urg'u bersa, yuridik matnlar identifikatsiyasida o'z joniga qasd qilishga qaratilgan xatlar, talab shakldagi so'rovnomalar matnlari, e-mail xabarlarini ajratib ko'rsatadi. I. K. Brinyev fikriga ko'ra yuridik tilshunoslikda lingvistik ekspertizani turlarga ajratish muhim ahamiyat kasb etmaydi. Eng muhimi sohagadoir yetuk mutaxassis kadrlarni tayyorlashdan iborat. L. V. Azhnyuk lingvistik ekspertizaning maxsus bilimlar talab qilinadigan ikki asosiy turini ko'rsatadi: Birinchidan, umumiy axborot vositalaridagi yoki boshqa biron bir yo'nalishda nashr etilgan umumiy matnlar (raqamli va bosma umumiy axborot vositalari, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar, televidenie va radio matnlaridasturlar, og'zaki taqdimotlar, reklama matnlari, tovarlarni iste'molchilar uchun ma'lumot va xizmatlar, firma nomlari va boshqalar). Bunda til huquqiy tartibga solish vositasi sifatida ishlaydi. Ikkinchidan, sotsial munosabatlarni tartibga solish bo'yicha lingvistik ekspertiza. Bunda turli normativ-huquqiy hujjatlar, shaxsiy yozishmalar asosiy ob'ekt bo'lib xizmat qiladi. U o'z fikrini quyidagi misol orqali dalillaydi: Ipotekashartnomasining X bandida ipoteka egasi nazarda tutilgan omonatchiga o'ziga xos ma'noda rasmiy talabni ma'lum tarzda yuboradi sabablari (bu ma'lum bir huquqiy natijaga ega). Ushbu ipoteka shartnomasining Z bandi ipoteka egasi depozitga rasmiy xabarnoma yuborishi bilan ta'minlaydi boshqa sabablarga ko'ra ma'lum ma'no (bu boshqa qonuniy natijaga ega). Ipoteka egasi omonatchiga bitta rasmiy hujjat (ariza -talab) yuboradi, bu bir vaqtning o'zida rasmiy xabarni ham, rasmiy talabni ham anglatadi. Depozit bunday harakatlarning qonuniyligini shubha ostiga qo'yadi va qonuniylarni sharhlaydi. L. V. Azhnyuk tomonidan belgilangan tarkibiy qismlar boshqa olimlar va mutaxassislar tomonidan berilgan mulohazalarga nisbatan solishtirganda umumiyroq xarakter kasb etadi. Olim ikki turga ajratishda asosiy xususiyatlarga tayanadi va shunga ko'ra bo'linishni ma'qul topadi. Anatoliy Baranov tomonidan

taklif etilgan lingvistik ekspertiza tarkibiy qismlarida tashkil etish shakliga ko'ra ajartirilgan deyish mumkin.

- rasmiy ekspertiza (sudning talabiga binoan amalga oshiriladi va u yuridik maqomga ega;

- tashabbus ekspertizasi (har qanday manfaatdorning talabiga binoan amalga oshiriladi (jismaniy yoki yuridik shaxs). Ko'rinadiki, Bunda muallif lingvistik ekspertizaning asosiy parametrlariga urg'u berib o'tadi. Har doim ham lingvistik ekspertiza o'tkazishga ehtiyoj tug'ilmaydi. Sud jarayonida ayblanuvchi, gumondor, guvoh ko'rsatmalari, mavjud dalillar tahliliga asosan mavjud qonun hujjatlariga ko'ra sud hukmi chiqariladi. Biroq shunday vaziyatlar yuzaga keladiki, bunda nafaqat mavjud qonun hujjatlari, yuridik bilimlar, balki maxsus lingvistik bilimlarga ham ehtiyoj tug'iladi. Xususan, haqorat va obro'sizlantirish, mansabdor shaxs mavqeyiga putur yetkazish kabi ayblovlar; yoki turli ko'rinishdagi anonim xatlar va yozma matnlar avtorizatsiyasi masalasiga oydinlik kiritish (muallifning o'zi yozganmi yo'qmi, tashqi ta'sir sharoiti bormi yo'qmi, fonetik-leksik va grammatik jihatdan qaysi hudud vakillariga nutqiga xos? Va h.k) kabi holatlarda lingvist-ekspertning bilimi va tajribasiga ehtiyoj tug'iladi. Yuqorida keltirilgan A.N. Baranov ajratgan lingvistik ekspertizaning birinchi ko'rinishi ayni shu va shu singari vaziyatlarda tayinlanadi. Yuridik va filologiya fanlari doktori, O.E. Kutafina nomidagi Moskva davlat universiteti professori E.I. Galyashining lingvistik ekspertizada lingvistik va huquqiy jihatlarni farqlash, ekstremistik materiallar lingvistik ekspertizasi, metod va metodologiya masalasi yuzasidan qator tadqiqotlar amalga oshirgan. Xususan, o'z tadqiqotlarida lingvistik ekspertizaning quyidagi turlarini ajratib ko'rsatadi:

- Sarlavha matnlarining lingvistik ekspertizasi (nomlash bo'yicha);

- Normativ-huquqiy hujjat va aktlarning lingvistik ekspertizasi;

- Ommaviy axborot vositalari matnlari va tashviqot materiallari, xatlar, manzillar lingvistik ekspertizasi;

- Fan, adabiyot va san'at asarlarini lingvistik ekspertizasi;

- Har qanday nutq materialining lingvistik ekspertizasi. Lingvistik ekspertiza o'tkazish jarayonining tarkibiy qismlari keyinchalik yana takomillashtirildi. Ushbu qatorga reklama matnlarining lingvistik ekspertizasi; og'zaki va yozma nutqning lingvistik ekspertizasi, birlashtirilgan savdo belgilari

va xizmat ko'rsatish belgilari; ekstremistik materiallarning lingvistik ekspertizasikabilar kiritildi. So'nggi yillarda ilm-fan va ijtimoiy-siyosiy aloqlarning rivojlanishi natijasida savdobelgilari, shuningdek, nomlanish bo'yicha turli yangi elementlar jadallik bilan kirib kela boshladi. Ushbu nomlar va belgilar ayrim xususiyatlari bilan xalqning milliy ko'rinishi, xususiyatlariga ta'sir ko'rsatmay qolmaydi. Buning natijasi o'laroq, savdo belgilari lingvistik ekspertizasiga ehtiyoj tug'iladi. Turli lingvistik adabiyotlarda, shuningdek, muayyan yuridik nashrlardasavdo belgisi atamasi "tijorat nominatsiyasi" atamasi bilan birgalikda qo'llanilmoqda. Shu bilan birga, muhokama qilingan tushunchalarning aniq bo'linishi mavjud emas. Amaldagi qonunchilikda tovar belgisi ayrimyuridik yoki jismoniy shaxslarning tovarlarini boshqa yuridik yoki jismoniy shaxslarning o'xshash tovarlaridan ajratib turadigan belgi sifatida belgilanadi. Xuddi shunday ta'riflingvistik adabiyotda ham uchraydi . T.A.Sobolevava A. V. Superanskayaning bayon etishicha, : "Tovar belgisi -bu tovarni tasarruf etish, foyda olish va sifatsiz mahsulotni etkazib berish uchun zarar etkazish bo'yicha eksklyuziv huquq kimga tegishli ekanligini ko'rsatadigan tijorat mulkining maxsus belgisidir". Savdo markalaritijorat nomiga o'xshash funksiyalarni bajaradi, xususan, farqlovchi, ma'lumot beruvchi, nominativ, jozibali va boshqalar. Demak, savdo belgilari ham axborot tashish funksiyasini bajaradi. Savdo markalari xavfsizlik va kafolat funksiyalarini bajarishi lozim. Xulosa. Yuqorida lingvistik ekspertologiyaning tarkibiy qismlari masalasi xususida fikr yuritishga harakat qildik. Ko'rinadiki, har bir bildirilgan fikr bir-birini takrorlamaydi, ayni vaqtda, bir-birini taqazo etadi. Lingvistik ekspertizaning ushbu turlari jahon tajribasida tahlilqilingan va asoslangan. Biroqo'zbekcha matnlar(og'zaki va yozma) milliy-etnik xususiyatlarga ega bo'lib, bunday matnlarni lingvistik ekspertiza qilisho'ziga xos xususiyat kasb etadi. Xususan, o'zbek adabiy tilidagi matnlar va o'zbek shevalaridagi matnlar bir-biriga aslo o'xshamaydi. Ularni farqlash, matn avtorizatsiyasini aniqlashda qo'llaniladigan usul va uslublarni ham turlicha bo'lishi tabiiydir. Lingvistik ekspertiza turlarini belgilashda masalaning ana shu jihatlariga ham e'tibor qaratish zarur deb hisoblaymiz. Fikrlarimizni umumlashtirib aytadigan bo'lsak, lingvistik ekspertiza o'tkazishda quyidagilarni ham tarkibiy qismlar sirasiga kiritish o'zbek yozma matnlari lingvistik ekspertizasi uchun maqsadga muvofiq:

- Dialektologik materiallar lingvistik ekspertizasi;

•Noverbal nutq vositalari orqali bayon etilgan nutq ekspertizasi(imoshoralar)Fanlararo jadala integratsiya o'zaro hamkorlik va muammolarning amaliy yechim topishigiga ko'mak beradi. Shu nuqtayi nazardan lingvistik bilimlar yuridik sohada tartibga solish ob'ekti sifatida ishlaydi.Endilikda yurisprudensiya va tilshunoslikning o'zaro hamkorligi yuzaga keladigan muammolarning xolisona yechimiga xizmat qiladi.Bu jarayonda lingvistik va huquqiy bilimlar birday ahamiyat kasb etadi.

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